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Effect of stocking density on growth performance and meat quality in Iberian pigs under extensive conditions

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Introduction: The Iberian pig production system under the “cebo de campo” category allows for a wide range of stocking densities, potentially leading to variability in productive performance and meat quality. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of two contrasting stocking densities (15 vs 100 pigs/ha) on growth performance, feed efficiency, carcass traits, and meat quality in purebred Iberian pigs.

Methods: Twenty castrated male pigs were allocated to two treatments: low stocking density with access to pasture (LOW) and high stocking density without pasture access (HIGH) during a 74-day finishing period. Both groups received identical concentrate allowances.

Result: Pigs reared at high stocking density showed greater average daily gain ($P = 0.049$) and tended to have improved feed conversion ratio. These differences were mainly observed during the late fattening phase. Backfat thickness was higher in the HIGH group ($P = 0.008$), whereas no significant differences were detected in carcass yield or prime cuts. Meat quality traits, including colour, intramuscular fat, antioxidant content, and fatty acid profile, were largely unaffected by stocking density.

Conclusion: Overall, the results suggest that increased stocking density under outdoor conditions may improve productive performance without compromising meat quality, with differences primarily driven by variations in energy expenditure rather than pasture intake.

KEYWORDS

exercise, fat deposition, feed efficiency, outdoor fattening, space allowance

1 Introduction

For The Iberian pig is a local breed originating from the southwestern regions of Spain. Historically, this breed has been reared under free-range conditions; Mediterranean woodland ecosystem known as the *dehesa*. However, the limited geographic extent of the *dehesa*, combined with the growing demand for Iberian pig products, has led to the incorporation of alternative production systems. These systems rely on concentrate-based diets during the finishing phase and give rise to various quality standards for the resulting products. Currently, the Spanish quality standard for Iberian pig products (Royal Decree 4/2014) establishes the minimum production requirements that animals must meet so that products may qualify for each of the categories defined in this standard hereby ensuring product homogeneity and authenticity

within each one. Specifically, this regulatory framework establishes four commercial categories -identified by distinct label colours -applicable to both fresh meat and dry-cured products such as ham, shoulder, and loin (Royal Decree 4/2014). According to this standard, the commercial categories labelled *Black* and *Red* correspond to products obtained from 100% pure Iberian pigs and from crossbred Iberian × Duroc pigs with 50–75% Iberian breed percentage, respectively; in both cases, animals are finished under the *montanera* system (free-range fattening in *dehesa* with animals fed exclusively on *ad libitum* acorns and pasture during the autumn–winter period). The *White* label applies to products derived from animals with at least 50% Iberian breed purity, reared in intensive systems and fed exclusively on commercial feed. Finally, the *Green* label might be placed halfway between the previous labels. This category, also referred to as “*cebo de campo*,” encompasses products from animals with at least 50% Iberian breed purity that may be raised either in extensive systems, characterised by low stocking densities (15 pigs per hectare) (Royal Decree 1221/2009), or in more intensive outdoor systems, where stocking densities may reach up to 100 pigs per hectare (Royal Decree 4/2014). Consequently, this broad range of production conditions presents important challenges for the *Green* category, particularly in terms of standardising production practices and ensuring the homogeneity of products commercialised under this label. In fact, a recent qualitative study based on in-depth semi-structured interviews with farmers and industry stakeholders highlighted the need to improve the definition and characterisation of animals classified as *cebo de campo* (Ortiz et al., 2020). Thus, the production of animals under the *Green* category at low stocking densities, and therefore within extensive systems, may involve free access to natural resources such as pasture when the final fattening phase coincides with periods of pasture availability (e.g., spring or autumn). The lower pig-per-hectare ratio also promotes greater physical activity compared with animals raised under more intensive conditions within the same category, thereby influencing overall animal behaviour and potentially affecting both productive performance and meat quality characteristics. In this regard (Rodríguez-Estévez et al., 2010), reported that Iberian pigs raised under extensive conditions could consume an average of 2.7 ± 0.22 kg of grass per day, which may contribute to improved average daily gain in animals finished during periods of pasture availability, such as spring or autumn. However, it is also important to consider the impact of the additional energy expenditure associated with animal movement in these systems, which directly affects this parameter (Rodríguez-Estévez et al., 2010).

Beyond productive performance, differences in physical activity together with pasture intake may also influence carcass and meat quality. Several studies have reported exercise-related effects on multiple traits, including increased carcass length (Geverink et al., 1998), enhanced fat infiltration, modifications in muscle fibre type composition and higher heme pigment content (Andrés et al., 2001) and, consequently, changes in meat colour, as well as alterations in the intramuscular fat fatty acid profile (Daza et al., 2009). Pasture intake may further contribute to these effects, given its high proportion of polyunsaturated fatty acids and antioxidants such as α -tocopherol (Rey et al., 2006).

Therefore, in this context, it is necessary to evaluate the impact of the potential variability in production conditions allowed by the current legislative framework for the *Green* category, to clarify its

effects on animal performance as well as on the resulting carcass and meat quality. This would, in turn, enhance transparency throughout the value chain for products classified under this category and generate knowledge on the factors that determine product homogeneity within it. Understanding these effects is also crucial for producers, policymakers and consumers, especially given growing societal concerns regarding animal welfare and sustainability, making the characterization of trade-offs between productive efficiency and other production system attributes within the *cebo de campo* category particularly relevant.

Based on previous research in other pig production systems and the specific characteristics of Iberian pig fattening, we hypothesised that contrasting stocking densities would differentially affect productive efficiency and carcass characteristics, with potential trade-offs between growth performance and body composition depending on the level of physical activity and access or not to natural resources. Therefore, the aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of two contrasting stocking densities (15 vs 100 pigs/ha) representing the extremes within the *cebo de campo* category permitted by the current legislative framework on growth performance, feed efficiency, carcass characteristics and meat quality traits of purebred Iberian pigs.

2 Materials and methodology

All animal handling procedures during the experimental period were conducted in accordance with Council Directive 2008/120/EC and Spanish legislation on animal welfare (Royal Decree 1392/2012 and Royal Decree 1221/2009) for extensive pig production systems. Since all procedures were considered standard husbandry practices, no specific ethical approval was required according to the criteria of the Animal Ethics Committee for Animal Experimentation of the University of Extremadura (Royal Decree 53/2013).

2.1 Animals and experimental design

The experiment was conducted at the Valdesequera experimental farm belonging to Centre of Scientific and Technological Research of Extremadura (CICYTEX), located in Badajoz province, southwestern Spain. Twenty purebred Iberian male pigs, surgically castrated and born in April 2024, were used in this study. At the beginning of the fattening period (early April 2025), animals were 12 months old.

Pigs were randomly allocated to two experimental treatments differing in stocking density: LOW (10 animals in a 0.67 ha paddock; 14.9 pigs/ha) and HIGH (10 animals in a 0.1 ha pen; 100 pigs/ha), with no significant differences in initial body weight (BW) between groups ($P = 1.00$). Both systems represent the extremes within the “*cebo de campo*” category (*Green* label) according to the legislative framework governing Iberian pig production. Specifically, (Royal Decree 4/2014) sets a minimum surface allowance of 100 m² per animal during the fattening phase, which corresponds to a maximum theoretical stocking density of 100 pigs per hectare. In addition, the decree requires animals to be finished in extensive holdings complying with (Royal Decree 1221/2009), which establishes an explicit maximum limit of 15 fattening pigs per hectare.

The fattening period lasted 74 days until slaughter. Animals in LOW had access to natural pasture resources, whereas those in

TABLE 1 Ingredients and nutrient composition of compound feed offered during the experiment.

Finishing diet	
Ingredients (g/kg)	
Barley	443
Wheat	400
Corn	116
Lard ¹	15.0
Calcium carbonate	12.5
Vitamin-Mineral premix ²	9.00
Sodium chloride	4.50
Nutrient composition (g/kg)	
Dry matter	892
Ash	38.1
Crude protein	102
Crude fat	32.0
Crude fibre	32.9
Net energy (kcal/kg)	2,474

¹Product of Intexur S.L. (Higuera la Real, Spain). Fatty acid profile (%): myristic acid (C14:0) 1.4, palmitic acid (C16:0) 25.0, palmitoleic acid (C16:1) 2.8, margaric acid (C17:0) 0.3, margaroleic acid (C17:1) 0.3, stearic acid (C18:0) 12.8, oleic acid (C18:1) 47.2, linoleic acid (C18:2) 7.4, α -linolenic acid (C18:3 n-3) 0.5, arachidic acid (C20:0) 0.2, gadoleic acid (C20:1) 1.1, eicosadienoic acid (C20:2 n-6) 0.4, dihomog- γ -linolenic acid (C20:3 n-6) 0.1, arachidonic acid (C20:4 n-6) 0.1, eicosatrienoic acid (C20:3 n-3) 0.1, docosapentaenoic acid (C22:5 n-3, DPA) 0.1. Other fatty acids <0.1%.²Vitamin-mineral premix (Nutrición y Gestión S.L., Lobón, Spain) providing vitamins A, D₃, E and B-complex; trace elements (Fe, Cu, Mn, Zn, I, Se); enzymes including phytase, β -glucanase and xylanase; probiotics (*Bacillus licheniformis* and *B. subtilis*); and amino acids (lysine, methionine, threonine), including a specialized formulation for Iberian pigs.

HIGH had no access to grazing due to limited space and absence of vegetation cover in the pen.

2.2 Housing and feeding management

Both experimental systems provided shade shelters and *ad libitum* access to water. In LOW, water troughs were located approximately 200 m away from the feeding area, requiring animals to walk this distance regularly. In contrast, HIGH had multiple water points distributed throughout the facility to ensure easy access.

Animals were individually identified with ear tags and fed twice daily (morning and afternoon) using individual feeding stations. Each pig had access to a separate feeding space where a controlled amount of concentrate feed was offered. Feed allowance was progressively adjusted according to BW evolution, increasing from 2.5 kg/d during the initial period to 4.0 kg/d by the end of the fattening phase. Feed was offered in individual feeders, and allowances were adjusted to ensure complete consumption with minimal refusals. Feed intake did not differ between treatments as both groups received identical allowances. The same commercial compound feed was provided to both treatments. Chemical composition and ingredients of the compound feed are shown in Table 1.

Natural pasture was continuously available in LOW throughout the experimental period, whereas in HIGH, pasture growth was prevented by high grazing pressure, resulting in negligible grazing opportunities. To characterise the nutritional quality of this

resource, pasture samples were collected on three occasions throughout the fattening period, with five samples taken per sampling event. Samples were oven-dried at 65°C to constant weight and analysed in duplicate by near-infrared spectroscopy (NIRS) for chemical composition. Mean pasture composition on a dry matter (DM) basis was crude protein (CP) 87 g/kg, neutral detergent fibre (NDF) 553 g/kg, and energy 0.85 UFL/kg, consistent with typical of *dehesa* grasslands during spring (Serrano et al., 2018). Individual pasture intake could not be quantified under the conditions of this study, as is standard in stocking density research.

2.3 Growth performance and feed efficiency

Animals were weighed individually at the beginning of the experiment - beginning of the fattening period- (day 0) and subsequently every 14 days (days 14, 28, 42, 56, and 70) using a livestock digital scale. On day 73, pigs were weighed to obtain the final BW. The following day (day 74), after 24 hours of fasting, animals were weighed again to determine the fasted body weight before transport to the slaughterhouse.

Average daily gain (ADG) and feed conversion ratio (FCR) were calculated for the overall fattening period (days 0-73). Additionally, the fattening period was divided into two phases: early fattening (days 0-35) and late fattening (days 35-73) to evaluate potential temporal changes in growth performance.

2.4 Slaughter procedure and sampling

At the end of the fattening period (day 74), pigs were fasted for 24 hours to obtain fasted body weight. Feed was provided to animals prior to loading and transport to a commercial slaughterhouse (Sierra de Barbellido, Salvaleón, Badajoz, Spain) located approximately 1.5 hours from the experimental farm. Transport was carried out in a ventilated truck. Upon arrival at the abattoir, animals were held in lairage pens with access to water for less than 24 hours before slaughter. Slaughter procedures complied with Council Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009. Pigs were stunned using carbon dioxide (CO₂) and subsequently exsanguinated. Standard commercial procedures were followed for scalding, dehairing, evisceration, and carcass splitting.

Carcass weight (CW), including kidneys and perirenal fat, was recorded after dressing. Carcass yield (CY) was calculated as: $CY (\%) = (CW/\text{fasted BW}) \times 100$. Backfat thickness was measured at the last rib on the left side of each carcass using a digital calliper, as this is the standard reference point for backfat assessment in pigs. Carcasses were quartered following standard commercial procedures for Iberian pigs. Each ham, shoulder, and loin was weighed individually after removal and trimming of external fat. Ham weight (HW), shoulder weight (SW), and loin weight (LW) represent the combined weight of both left and right pieces per animal. Prime cuts weight (PCW) was calculated as $PCW = HW + SW + LW$. The yields of hams (HY), shoulders (SY), loins (LY), and prime cuts (PCY) were calculated relative to CW using the following equations, according to the methodology described by (García-Gudiño et al., 2013):

$$HY (\%) = (HW/CW) \times 100$$

$$SY(\%) = (SW/CW) \times 100$$

$$LY(\%) = (LW/CW) \times 100$$

$$PCY(\%) = (PCW/CW) \times 100$$

Subsequently, the *Longissimus thoracis et lumborum* and *Serratus ventralis* muscles from the left side of each carcass were excised and transported under refrigerated conditions (2–4 °C) in a refrigerated van to the CICYTEX facilities (Badajoz, Spain). Samples were stored at 4 °C for 24 hours post-mortem before meat quality analyses were conducted.

2.5 Meat quality analysis

2.5.1 Instrumental colour

The colour attributes L^* (lightness), a^* (redness) and b^* (yellowness) were assessed on the *Longissimus thoracis et lumborum* and *Serratus ventralis* muscles using a Minolta CR-400 colorimeter (Minolta Camera, Osaka, Japan), following (AMSA, 2011) recommendations. From these primary coordinates, chroma (C^*), which reflects colour saturation, was computed as $C^* = \sqrt{a^{*2} + b^{*2}}$, and the hue angle (H°) was obtained using $H^\circ = \arctan\left(\frac{b^*}{a^*}\right)$ (Wyszcecki and Stiles, 1982). To account for within-sample variability, colour was recorded at five randomly chosen locations on each muscle, and the average of these readings was used for subsequent statistical analyses.

2.5.2 Chemical colour

The concentration of myoglobin and its chemical forms were assessed (Pujol et al., 2023; Tang et al., 2004). Samples were homogenised in phosphate buffer (pH 6.85) using an IKA ULTRA-TURRAX T-25 homogeniser. The resulting mixture was filtered through Whatman No. 1 paper, and the absorbance of the filtrate was recorded at 503, 525, 557, 582 and 700 nm with a UV–visible spectrophotometer (Agilent Cary 60). These absorbance values were subsequently used to calculate total myoglobin content and the proportions of its different chemical forms, applying the corresponding equations in which A denotes absorbance at wavelength λ (nm), 7.6 is the millimolar extinction coefficient at 525 nm, and 17 kDa represents the approximate molecular weight of myoglobin.

$$Mb \left[\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{g product}} \right] = (\lambda_{525} - 700) \times \frac{1 \text{ mM Mb}}{7.6} \times \frac{1 \text{ mmol}}{\text{mM}} \times \frac{17 \text{ g Mb}}{1 \text{ mmol Mb}} \times \frac{0.03 \text{ (L)}}{\text{peso muestra}} \times \frac{1000 \text{ mg}}{\text{(g)}} \times \frac{1}{\text{g}}$$

$$\text{Deoxymyoglobin (\%)} = (-0.543 \left(\frac{\lambda_{582}}{\lambda_{525}} \right) + 1.594 \left(\frac{\lambda_{557}}{\lambda_{525}} \right) + 0.552 \left(\frac{\lambda_{503}}{\lambda_{525}} \right) - 1.329) \times 100$$

$$\text{Oxymyoglobin (\%)} = (0.722 \left(\frac{\lambda_{582}}{\lambda_{525}} \right) - 1.594 \left(\frac{\lambda_{557}}{\lambda_{525}} \right) - 0.552 \left(\frac{\lambda_{503}}{\lambda_{525}} \right) + 2.599) \times 100$$

$$\text{Metamyoglobin (\%)} = (-0.159 \left(\frac{\lambda_{582}}{\lambda_{525}} \right) - 0.085 \left(\frac{\lambda_{557}}{\lambda_{525}} \right) + 1.262 \left(\frac{\lambda_{503}}{\lambda_{525}} \right) - 0.520) \times 100$$

2.5.3 Intramuscular fat

Intramuscular fat (IMF) was analysed according to Folch et al. (1957) and results were expressed as g/100 g.

2.5.4 Antioxidants

Tocopherol compounds were isolated by saponifying the samples with a solution containing 11.5% KOH in an EtOH/H₂O mixture (55:45), incorporating ascorbic acid to prevent oxidative degradation. The extracts were then analysed using an Agilent 1100 Series HPLC system equipped with a Kromasil silica column (5 μm , 150 \times 4.6 mm) and a matching silica guard column (10 μm). Separation was achieved with a mobile phase of hexane:isopropanol:ethanol (98.5:1:0.5, v/v) at 1 mL/min, and detection was performed fluorimetrically ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 295 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 330 \text{ nm}$; Agilent 1200 Series). Tocopherols were identified and quantified by comparison with calibration standards of α - and γ -tocopherol (0.2–14 $\mu\text{g/mL}$), and results were expressed as μg of α -tocopherol per gram of sample.

2.5.5 Fatty acid profile

Lipid extraction was carried out following the method of Folch et al. (1957). Fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) were produced by acid-catalysed transesterification using sulfuric acid (5% H₂SO₄ in methanol) and sodium methoxide, according to (Sandler and Karo, n.d.). The resulting FAME were analysed by gas chromatography on an Agilent 6890 system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) equipped with a DB-23 capillary column (60 m \times 0.25 mm i.d., 0.5 μm film thickness; Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA, USA) and a flame ionization detector (FID). Injector and detector temperatures were set to 260 and 280 °C, respectively. The oven temperature program was 185 °C for 2 min, then increased to 220 °C at 5 °C·min⁻¹ and held for 40 min. Fatty acids were identified by comparing retention times with those of a certified FAME standard mixture (Sigma-Aldrich, Supelco 37 Component FAME Mix, CRM47885; St. Louis, MO, USA) and quantified accordingly. Results were expressed as mg FAME per g of fat.

2.5.6 Oxidative status

Lipid hydroperoxides (primary oxidation products) were determined following Freire et al. (2017) with minor modifications. Briefly, 2 g of sample were homogenized with 25 mL of chloroform/methanol (1:1, v/v) for 30 s at 4 °C. The homogenate was then combined with 6 mL of 0.5% NaCl and centrifuged at 3000 \times g for 30 min at 4 °C. Lipid hydroperoxides were quantified in the chloroform layer (200 μL) according to the method described by Shantha and Decker (1994). Cumene hydroperoxide (CHP) was used for calibration, and results were reported as mmol CHP equivalents per kg of sample.

2.6 Statistical analysis

Results were expressed as least squares means with their standard error. Statistical analyses were performed using SAS OnDemand for Academics (Version 9.4; SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA). A general linear model (PROC GLM) was used to evaluate the effect of stocking density on growth performance, feed efficiency, carcass characteristics, prime cuts yield, and meat quality

FIGURE 1

Evolution of body weight during the fattening period in Iberian pigs reared at low (15 pigs/ha) and high (100 pigs/ha) stocking densities. Values are means with standard error bars ($n=10$ per treatment). The vertical dashed line indicates the division between early (0–35 d) and late (35–73 d) fattening phases.

parameters (instrumental and chemical colour, intramuscular fat and antioxidant and fatty acid profile), according to the following model:

$$Y_{ij} = \mu + S_i + e_{ij}$$

where Y_{ij} represents the observed variable, μ is the overall mean, S_i denotes the effect of stocking density (LOW vs HIGH), and e_{ij} is the residual error term. Statistical significance was set at $P \leq 0.05$, with tendencies discussed when $0.05 < P \leq 0.10$.

3 Results

3.1 Growth performance and feed efficiency

BW evolution throughout the fattening period is shown in Figure 1. Both treatments exhibited similar growth patterns during the initial phase, with BW remaining comparable until approximately day 42. From day 56 onwards, pigs in HIGH showed higher BW compared to those in LOW, although these differences did not reach statistical significance at individual time points.

Growth performance and feed efficiency parameters are presented in Table 2. Over the entire fattening period, pigs in HIGH achieved significantly greater ADG than those in LOW ($P = 0.049$), resulting in a numerically higher final BW. FCR tended to be more favourable in HIGH compared to LOW ($P = 0.065$).

When considering both phases of the fattening period separately, contrasting patterns emerged. During the early phase, no significant differences were observed between treatments for either ADG or FCR. However, in the late fattening phase, HIGH exhibited significantly higher ADG ($P = 0.020$) and superior FCR ($P = 0.030$) compared to LOW.

TABLE 2 Effect of stocking density on growth performance and feed efficiency of Iberian pigs.

	LOW (n = 10)	HIGH (n = 10)	P-value
Overall period (0–73 d)			
Initial BW (kg)	104.7 ± 1.22	104.7 ± 1.42	1.000
Final BW (kg)	156.7 ± 2.30	161.1 ± 2.88	0.243
ADG (kg/day)	0.693 ± 0.017	0.750 ± 0.020	0.049
FCR (kg/day)	4.64 ± 0.12	4.31 ± 0.12	0.065
Early phase (0–35 d)			
ADG (kg/day)	0.673 ± 0.026	0.680 ± 0.018	0.815
FCR (kg/day)	4.14 ± 0.15	4.11 ± 0.12	0.885
Late phase (35–73 d)			
ADG (kg/day)	0.637 ± 0.030	0.724 ± 0.013	0.020
FCR (kg/day)	5.21 ± 0.27	4.50 ± 0.08	0.030

Values are expressed as least squares means ± standard error. BW, body weight; ADG, average daily gain; FCR, feed conversion ratio; LOW, low stocking density (15 pigs/ha); HIGH, high stocking density (100 pigs/ha).

3.2 Carcass characteristics and prime cuts yield

Carcass traits and prime cuts performance are shown in Table 3. No significant differences were observed between treatments for fasted BW, carcass weight, carcass yield, or for the weights and yields of individual prime cuts (ham, shoulder, and loin).

The only significant difference was observed in backfat thickness measured at the last rib, with HIGH showing significantly greater fat deposition than LOW ($P = 0.008$).

3.3 Chemical and instrumental colour

The myoglobin content (Table 4) averaged approximately 2.6 mg/g in LTL and exceeded 5.8 mg/g in *Serratus ventralis* samples, with no significant differences observed between treatments. In terms of the distribution of myoglobin forms, metmyoglobin represented the largest fraction with around half of the total in both muscles, followed by oxymyoglobin, which accounted for more than 30%. Deoxymyoglobin showed the lowest proportion, remaining below 20% in all cases. In the LTL muscle, significant differences were observed in the relative proportions of oxymyoglobin and metmyoglobin, as animals reared at LOW stocking density displayed lower levels of the former and higher levels of the latter.

Regarding instrumental colour parameters (Table 4), stocking density during the finishing phase did not induce significant changes in any of the CIELab coordinates for either the LTL or *Serratus ventralis* muscles. Lightness, redness, and yellowness values were comparable between groups, and the same trend was observed for chroma and hue angle, indicating consistent colour saturation and tonality across treatments.

TABLE 3 Effect of stocking density on carcass characteristics and prime cuts yield of Iberian pigs.

	LOW (n = 10)	HIGH (n = 10)	P-value
Fasted BW (kg)	151.9 ± 2.49	157.0 ± 2.59	0.175
Carcass weight (kg)	120.2 ± 2.04	123.4 ± 2.19	0.304
Carcass yield (%)	79.15 ± 0.37	78.57 ± 0.22	0.230
Backfat thickness (cm)	5.75 ± 0.25	6.63 ± 0.28	0.008
Prime cuts weight (kg)			
Ham weight	11.15 ± 0.68	11.16 ± 0.70	0.950
Shoulder weight	7.33 ± 0.68	7.40 ± 0.68	0.711
Loin weight	1.83 ± 0.03	1.89 ± 0.04	0.228
Prime cuts yield (%)			
Ham	18.57 ± 0.14	18.13 ± 0.24	0.112
Shoulder	12.19 ± 0.19	12.00 ± 0.18	0.480
Loin	3.05 ± 0.05	3.06 ± 0.03	0.937
Total	33.80 ± 0.21	33.18 ± 0.38	0.155

Values are expressed as least squares means ± standard error. BW, body weight; LOW, low stocking density (15 pigs/ha); HIGH, high stocking density (100 pigs/ha); Backfat thickness was measured at the last rib (14th thoracic vertebra).

3.4 Antioxidants and fatty acid profile

Intramuscular fat (IMF) content (Table 4) was comparable between muscles, ranging from 8.07 to 9.03 g/100 g, and was not affected by stocking density during the finishing period in either muscle.

Regarding antioxidant composition (Table 5), α-tocopherol levels did not differ significantly between stocking density groups in either muscle. In contrast, γ-tocopherol concentration in the *Serratus ventralis* was significantly higher in animals raised in LOW stocking density, a pattern that was not observed in the LTL muscle.

In relation to the lipid profile, both muscles showed a fatty acid composition dominated by MUFAs, followed by SFAs and, to a lesser extent, PUFAs, regardless of the stocking density (Table 5). More in detail, In the LTL muscle, MUFAs accounted for approximately 54–56% of total quantified fatty acids (229.38–239.25 mg/g), whereas SFAs represented around 39–44% (167.42–189.47 mg/g), with a similar distribution for *Serratus ventralis*. Oleic acid was the predominant fatty acid in both muscles, while palmitic and stearic acids were the main saturated fatty acids and linoleic acid the major PUFA. On the other hand, no significant differences between LOW and HIGH stocking density were detected for the main fatty acids, or the total SFA, MUFA and PUFA fractions (p>0.05).

Finally, primary lipid oxidation (peroxide value) (Table 5), used as an index of lipid oxidative status, showed no significant differences between groups in either of the muscles assessed.

4 Discussion

Stocking density exerted significant effects on productive performance, with pigs in HIGH achieving superior growth rates and feed conversion efficiency compared to those in LOW. The moderate nutritional quality of pasture available in LOW (8.7% CP, 0.85 UFL/kg DM), typical of Mediterranean grasslands during spring, suggests that performance differences were primarily driven by energy expenditure associated with activity rather than by nutritional deficiencies in available forage. Whilst extensive literature exists on space allowance effects in confined pig production systems, recent reviews have highlighted significant inconsistencies in scientific approaches and emphasised the need for controlled studies replicating commercial conditions to understand the relationship between space provision and productive outcomes (Chidgey, 2024). In the context of outdoor fattening systems such as *cebo de campo*, where both systems provided space well above

TABLE 4 Effect of stocking density on Chemical and instrumental colour of *Longissimus thoracis et lumborum* and *Serratus ventralis* muscles of Iberian pigs.

Parameter	LTL muscle			<i>Serratus ventralis</i> muscle		
	LOW (n=10)	HIGH (n=10)	P-value	LOW (n=10)	HIGH (n=10)	P-value
Myoglobin and chemical forms of myoglobin						
Mb (mg/g)	2.65 ± 0.07	2.67 ± 0.08	0.869	5.86 ± 0.22	5.88 ± 0.26	0.938
DeoxMb (%)	17.18 ± 0.49	17.34 ± 0.22	0.790	16.63 ± 0.58	15.96 ± 0.86	0.511
OxMb (%)	32.58 ± 0.94	35.97 ± 0.46	0.008	41.41 ± 1.27	42.7 ± 2.10	0.588
MetaMb (%)	49.45 ± 0.98	46.87 ± 0.98	0.036	43.65 ± 0.95	41.37 ± 1.35	0.174
Instrumental colour coordinates (CIELab)						
L*	47.1 ± 0.71	47.95 ± 0.81	0.437	36.52 ± 0.62	36.04 ± 0.67	0.609
a*	11.18 ± 0.16	10.98 ± 0.26	0.512	12.61 ± 0.37	12.17 ± 0.25	0.369
b*	5.50 ± 0.14	5.75 ± 0.19	0.299	5.93 ± 0.30	5.89 ± 0.20	0.928
C	12.62 ± 0.40	12.41 ± 0.29	0.699	14.07 ± 0.42	13.53 ± 0.30	0.338
H	26.64 ± 0.48	27.6 ± 0.47	0.259	25.46 ± 0.31	25.78 ± 0.43	0.539

Values are expressed as least squares means ± standard error. Mb, myoglobin; DeoxMb, deoxy myoglobin; OxMb, oxy myoglobin; MetaMb, metmyoglobin. LOW, low stocking density (15 pigs/ha); HIGH, high stocking density (100 pigs/ha).

TABLE 5 Antioxidant composition, fatty acid profile and oxidative status of *Longissimus thoracis et lumborum* and *Serratus ventralis* muscles of Iberian pigs.

Parameter	LTL muscle			<i>Serratus ventralis</i> muscle		
	LOW (n=10)	HIGH (n=10)	P-value	LOW (n=10)	HIGH (n=10)	P-value
Antioxidant composition (µg/g)						
α-Tocopherol	3.05 ± 0.12	3.38 ± 0.23	0.201	4.58 ± 0.23	4.81 ± 0.14	0.437
γ-Tocopherol	0.12 ± 0.01	0.12 ± 0.01	0.811	0.15 ± 0.00	0.13 ± 0.00	0.044
IMF (g/100 g)	8.07 ± 0.34	9.03 ± 0.65	0.185	8.82 ± 0.36	8.71 ± 0.36	0.834
Fatty acid composition (mg/g)						
C16:0	124.74 ± 6.37	110.51 ± 7.60	0.168	109.18 ± 5.66	101.14 ± 5.56	0.335
C18:0	52.93 ± 3.39	46.28 ± 3.53	0.197	21.38 ± 1.31	42.39 ± 2.64	0.086
C18:1 n-9	194.89 ± 9.99	203.46 ± 14.66	0.625	49.60 ± 2.81	177.83 ± 10.40	0.346
C18:2 n-6	22.62 ± 1.31	22.47 ± 1.88	0.948	166.13 ± 6.90	23.07 ± 1.53	0.494
C18:3 n-3	1.62 ± 0.09	1.32 ± 1.05	0.058	24.50 ± 1.36	1.29 ± 0.07	0.002
C20:0	1.09 ± 0.05	1.09 ± 0.09	0.983	1.72 ± 0.086	0.94 ± 0.07	0.661
C20:1	1.25 ± 0.09	1.44 ± 0.13	0.229	0.98 ± 0.02	1.24 ± 0.08	0.285
ΣAGS	189.47 ± 10.17	167.42 ± 11.54	0.17	1.13 ± 0.11	152.96 ± 8.60	0.238
ΣAGMI	229.38 ± 11.71	239.25 ± 17.32	0.632	168.29 ± 8.81	208.16 ± 12.49	0.303
ΣAGPI	28.19 ± 1.70	27.89 ± 2.39	0.916	192.74 ± 8.30	28.46 ± 1.90	0.481
Oxidative status						
Peroxide Value (mEquiv HPC/Kg muestra)	0.26 ± 0.03	0.24 ± 0.02	0.578	0.16 ± 0.03	0.10 ± 0.03	0.183

Values are expressed as least squares means ± standard error. ΣAGS: sum of all saturated fatty acids detected (C10:0, C12:0, C14:0, C16:0, C17:0, C18:0, C20:0, C22:0); ΣMUFA: sum of all monounsaturated fatty acids detected (C16:1, C17:1, C18:1, C20:1, C22:1); ΣPUFA: sum of all polyunsaturated fatty acids detected (C18:2, C18:3, C20:2, C20:4). LOW, low stocking density (15 pigs/ha); HIGH, high stocking density (100 pigs/ha).

minimum welfare requirements, performance differences cannot be attributed to space restriction per se, but rather to the energy expenditure associated with resource distribution and activity patterns inherent to extensive systems. In low-density systems, greater space inherently involves increased physical activity: resource dispersal requires regular displacement (water located 200 m from feeding areas in this study), and pasture access promotes foraging behaviour (Daza et al., 2009). Previous research has shown that physical activity alters lipid metabolism and energy partitioning in fattening pigs, with locomotion and foraging accounting for substantial energy cost in grazing Iberian pigs (Rodríguez-Estévez et al., 2010). Foraging activity in restricted-fed pigs increases in response to protein or energy limitation (Jakobsen et al., 2015), suggesting that pigs in LOW may have increased foraging effort to compensate for the additional energy expenditure associated with locomotion and resource dispersal. These factors represent the integrated reality of extensive production rather than isolated variables. A critical consideration is that pigs in LOW had continuous access to natural pasture with modest but not negligible nutritional quality (8.7% CP, 0.85 UFL/kg DM), typical of Mediterranean grasslands during spring (Serrano et al., 2018).

Individual pasture intake was not quantified in this study, as is typical in stocking density research where direct measurement of grazing behaviour across large areas is impractical. Previous research on Iberian pigs grazing during *montanera* has shown that pasture can contribute substantially to intake, with fresh matter consumption reaching up to 2.7 kg/day when pigs forage freely without

supplementary feed (Rodríguez-Estévez et al., 2009). Whilst pasture availability and intake patterns likely differ between *montanera* and spring *cebo de campo* conditions, the potential for meaningful pasture contribution existed in LOW. Despite this potential, LOW pigs exhibited inferior efficiency compared to HIGH, strongly suggesting that the additional energy cost associated with resource dispersal and foraging outweighed any nutritional benefits from pasture intake, with performance differences driven primarily by energy expenditure rather than nutritional deficiencies.

A particularly noteworthy finding was the temporal pattern of treatment effects. Performance remained comparable between treatments during the early fattening phase (days 0-35) yet diverged markedly during the late fattening phase (days 35-73), when HIGH exhibited significantly superior growth and feed conversion efficiency compared to LOW (Figure 1). This temporal divergence helps explain how stocking density affects productive outcomes in *cebo de campo* fattening systems. The abrupt nature of this divergence, rather than a gradual decline, argues against pasture quality as the primary limiting factor. Had declining pasture quality been the main limiting factor, performance differences would have emerged gradually and progressively throughout the trial, tracking the seasonal decline in forage quality. Instead, the clear demarcation between phases aligns with the metabolic shift toward adipose tissue deposition that characterises late fattening in pigs (FEDNA, 2013). This temporal pattern indicates that energy expenditure, rather than pasture quality, drove the performance divergence. During late fattening, when fat deposition predominates, the energy cost of

locomotion and foraging in LOW diverted nutrients from adipose tissue accumulation, whereas HIGH pigs allocated more energy to fat accretion. This interpretation is consistent with the observed differences in carcass composition between treatments.

Beyond the performance differences discussed above, the only significant difference observed in carcass characteristics was backfat thickness, which was 15% greater in HIGH than LOW. This differential fat accretion occurred despite comparable carcass weights and lean tissue yields, indicating that the performance advantage in HIGH was allocated specifically towards adipose tissue deposition during the late fattening phase. Previous research in pigs has demonstrated that exercise and increased locomotion can reduce fat deposition whilst having minimal or neutral effects on lean tissue growth (Gondret et al., 2005; Daza et al., 2009), a pattern clear in the present results.

Regarding meat quality traits, the myoglobin content observed in fresh loin was similar to the values previously reported by Mayoral et al. (1999) for loins from animals finished under *montanera* conditions. In the present study, the potentially greater activity of pigs kept at lower stocking densities to water and graze did not appear to be sufficient to produce a significant increase in myoglobin concentration in either of the muscles evaluated. On the other hand, the increase in oxymyoglobin and the corresponding decrease in metmyoglobin observed in the LTL muscle are likely attributable to a technological factor during sample handling - specifically, greater exposure to oxygen- rather than to differences associated with stocking density. This interpretation is supported by the fact that both groups exhibited comparable post-mortem pH values, both at 45 minutes (6.03 ± 0.05 vs. 5.83 ± 0.09 ; $P = 0.263$) and at 24 hours (5.61 ± 0.02 vs. 5.59 ± 0.03 ; $P = 0.487$) for LOW and HIGH, respectively, since comparable pH conditions imply a similar redox balance and thus a similar equilibrium between myoglobin redox forms (Mancini and Hunt, 2005; Møller et al., 2003). In any case, the absence of differences in myoglobin content between treatments, together with comparable post-mortem pH were consistent with the lack of treatment effects on CIELab coordinates.

On the other hand, despite the significantly greater backfat thickness in HIGH, the stocking rate and the consequent access (or not) to pasture did not appear to substantially influence intramuscular lipid deposition in either of the muscles evaluated. This lack of effect may be explained by the fact that genetic predisposition, particularly the expression of key lipogenic genes (Villaplana-Velasco et al., 2021; Garrido et al., 2023), tends to play a more decisive role in intramuscular fat accumulation than moderate variations in management. Regarding the lack of differences in the fatty acid profile associated with stocking densities, it is consistent with the notion that intramuscular fat deposition and its fatty acid composition are strongly constrained by genotype-related adipogenicity (D'Souza et al., 2012) and therefore tend to be less responsive to moderate changes due to production conditions than subcutaneous fat. In addition, both groups received the same concentrate allowance, which likely dominated lipid supply. Thus, although pigs reared at low density had access to spring pasture, its contribution to total nutrient intake was not quantified but was probably modest relative to the concentrate-based feeding regime; consequently, any grazing-derived increase in PUFA intake may have been diluted within the intramuscular lipid pool. Concerning antioxidant composition, although γ -tocopherol in the *Serratus*

ventralis was statistically higher in LOW pigs, this difference should be interpreted cautiously. In Iberian pig studies, γ -tocopherol has been more strongly associated with acorn intake (Rey et al., 2006) which was not available during the period when animals under the low stocking rate accessed the pasture; thus, a clear nutritional mechanism linked to the feeding environment is unlikely. Moreover, absolute γ -tocopherol concentrations were very low in both groups and showed minimal dispersion, so small between-animal variation may have reached statistical significance without necessarily implying biological relevance. This interpretation is supported by the absence of parallel changes in α -tocopherol and by the lack of differences in peroxide values, suggesting that the oxidative status of the muscle lipids remained comparable between stocking densities. It should be noted that this study was conducted during spring, when pasture availability and nutritional quality are typically favourable in Mediterranean *dehesa* ecosystems. The relative contribution of pasture to performance differences between stocking densities may vary seasonally, particularly during periods of reduced pasture availability (summer) or increased energy requirements (winter), warranting further investigation to optimise production strategies within the *Green* label category throughout the year.

These results have important implications for stakeholders across the Iberian pig value chain. Under the experimental conditions evaluated, HIGH achieved approximately 8% greater ADG and 7% improved FCR compared to LOW, with efficiency gains concentrated during the late fattening phase when feed costs are highest. These productivity differences translate directly into reduced production costs per unit of carcass weight, offering clear economic advantages.

Nevertheless, LOW provides substantially greater space allowance and continuous access to spring pasture, attributes that are closer to traditional extensive husbandry practices. Importantly, both stocking density extremes produced meat with comparable intramuscular fat content, fatty acid composition, and oxidative stability, indicating that either approach can yield raw material with a broadly similar technological and nutritional profile for fresh and processed products. From this perspective, stocking density *per se* may not be a primary driver of the perceived lack of homogeneity among products marketed under the *Green* label, and other sources of variability (e.g., genetics, feeding strategies, finishing duration, seasonality, or pasture availability/quality) are likely to play a more decisive role.

For Iberian pig producers, these findings indicate that stocking density selection within the *Green* label framework involves balancing economic efficiency against other production system attributes. For the processing industry, both density extremes deliver suitable raw material quality, though with different production costs and carcass characteristics.

5 Conclusions

The *Green* label category for Iberian pig products permits stocking densities ranging from 15 to 100 pigs/ha under a single commercial designation. This study demonstrates that whilst stocking density and the consequent access (or not) to natural spring pasture markedly affects productive performance, meat quality remains comparable, with

intramuscular fat content, fatty acid profile, and oxidative stability unaffected by density-related differences in animal activity. These findings suggest that activity-related metabolic changes, at least within the range studied, do not substantially alter meat quality traits.

This dissociation between productive efficiency and meat quality reveals an important finding: HIGH and LOW stocking densities yield products of comparable quality but differ markedly in economic efficiency. HIGH delivers superior productive performance and feed conversion efficiency, thereby reducing costs per unit of output. Conversely, LOW, despite reduced productive efficiency, provides enhanced animal welfare through increased space allowance and continuous pasture access—attributes aligned with traditional extensive husbandry practices and increasingly valued by consumer segments prioritising production system transparency and animal welfare standards.

The coexistence of markedly different stocking densities within a single category underscores the need for clearer characterisation and communication of production conditions. Transparent differentiation of *Green* label products will be essential for decision-making by stakeholders in the Iberian pig value chain and for sustaining the competitiveness of Iberian pig products in high-quality markets where consumers increasingly value production attributes alongside intrinsic quality.

Data availability statement

The raw data supporting the conclusions of this article will be made available by the authors, without undue reservation.

Ethics statement

The animal study was approved by Ethics Committee for Animal Experimentation, University of Extremadura, Spain. The study was conducted in accordance with the local legislation and institutional requirements.

Author contributions

AO: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. DT: Funding acquisition,

Project administration, Writing – review & editing. MF: Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. LL: Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. JG-G: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing.

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Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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